

Preliminary Insights into Challenges in Electrospun Nanofibers from Hemp-Derived Cellulose

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Abstract

In this study, the fabrication of nanofibers from hemp-derived cellulose and cellulose acetate using electrospinning was investigated. Various solvent mixtures and concentrations were investigated to determine the optimum conditions for dissolving cellulose samples. The morphological and structural analyses of the cellulose and cellulose acetates were conducted using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). Additionally, the adsorption efficiency of cellulose acetate for methylene blue (MB), a common dye pollutant, was evaluated. This aspect of the study highlights the potential environmental applications of hemp-derived cellulose derivatives in wastewater treatment.

Keywords: Cellulose, electrospinning, hemp, nanofiber

Introduction

Cellulose, a highly abundant polymer, offers many advantages, such as renewability, biodegradability, biocompatibility, and non-toxicity. It can be sourced from various materials, including wood, cotton, hemp, algae, jute, corn, rice, wheat straw, and sisal. Electrospun cellulosic nanofibers, with their high surface area-to-volume ratio, exceptional flexibility, and impact resistance, hold immense potential in diverse fields such as biomedical applications, drug delivery, energy, and filtration [1]. However, the electrospinning of cellulose is a complex process, presenting a challenge due to its insolubility in most common solvents, a property attributed to inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Cellulose acetate, an esterification derivative of cellulose, stands out for its exceptional properties and favorable conditions for electrospinning [2]. In addition, the sorption efficiency of cellulose acetate nanofibers is particularly advantageous due to their high surface area and porous structure, which enhance their capacity to adsorb dyes and other pollutants.

Considering the strengths and weaknesses of cellulose and its derivatives, this study aimed to fabricate electrospun nanofibers using cellulose derived from hemp, a promising and renewable source. Additionally, the cellulose acetate was investigated for its potential in MB sorption. This study underscores the significant advantages of hemp-derived cellulose acetate in sorption applications, suggesting its efficacy in environmental remediation.

Materials and Method

Hemp fibers were sourced from hemp plants harvested in the Central Anatolia region of Türkiye. The hemp was washed with distilled water, dried, and pulverized into powder using a Wiley mill. The extraction of cellulose was conducted by a bleaching process utilizing a solution consisting of H₂O₂ (7%, v/v) and NaOH (4%, w/v) in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio, maintained at 60 °C for 3 hours in a water bath [3]. Then, the bleached cellulose fiber was acetylated to produce cellulose acetate by previously reported method [4]. Cellulose acetylation involves three stages: activation with glacial acetic acid and sulfuric acid, acetylation with acetic anhydride and sulfuric acid followed by hydrolysis. The mixture is divided as cellulose triacetate (CTA) and cellulose diacetate (CDA), which are filtered, washed, and dried. CTA is obtained by pouring the solution into pure water, while CDA is obtained by stirring with glacial acetic acid and water before precipitation [4].

The surface morphology was determined by an SEM (Carl Zeiss 300 VP), and the diameter of hemp and cellulose fibers were calculated using Fiji ImageJ software. Functional groups in hemp, cellulose, and their derivatives were identified by an FTIR spectrometer (PerkinElmer, USA) equipped with a UATR Diamond/ZnSe ATR (single reflection). TGA analysis of the samples was carried out by the TA

(TGA-SDT Q600) instrument. The crystallographic analysis of the samples was recorded by an XRD (Panalytical Empyrean) X-ray diffractometer with CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5444 \text{ \AA}$). Zeta potential and particle size measurements were performed in water (pH 7.0) by the Particle Analyzer (Anton Paar Litesizer 500).

In addition, cellulose was modified to support the formation of cellulose nanofibers by electrospinning. Cellulose was modified with 2,2,6,6-Tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (TEMPO) solution and potassium bromide for 1 h. Then, the sodium hypochlorite solution (12.5%) was added dropwise and stirred at room temperature to initiate TEMPO-mediated oxidation. TEMPO-modified cellulose was filtered and washed with water to pH 7 [5].

Cellulose and modified cellulose samples were subjected to solubility tests using various solvents (*N,N*-dimethylacetamide (DMAc)/lithium chloride (LiCl), tetrahydrofuran (THF), lithium hydroxide (LiOH), potassium hydroxide (KOH), 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ([BMIM]Cl), etc.) for nanofiber production. Various parameters were tested, including applied voltages ranging from 10 to 25 kV, needle-to-collector distances between 5 and 25 cm, and flow rates from 0.5 to 3.0 mL/h. The resulting cellulose-based nanostructures were characterized and subsequently utilized for MB sorption. To investigate the effect of solution pH on MB sorption, experiments were conducted with 5 mg of sorbent, an initial MB concentration of 5 mg L⁻¹, a 3 mL solution volume, and a 10-minute effect time, adjusting the pH with HCl or NaOH. For the effect of contact time at different concentrations, experiments used 10 mg of sorbent, pH 7, a 10 mL solution volume, and varying initial MB concentrations. Samples were taken at different times, filtered, and analyzed using a UV-vis spectrophotometer to assess the sorption efficiency.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows photographs of hemp (stalk and milled) and bleached cellulose. The white-cellulose fibers were obtained by milling brown hemp fibers and then were bleached to remove the non-cellulosic content. The fiber color changed after chemical treatment due to the removal of chromophore groups in lignin [3].

Figure 1. Photographic images of hemp (stalk) (a), milled hemp (b), and bleached cellulose (c)

The morphological properties of hemp and bleached cellulose were examined by SEM (Figure 2). Figure 2a shows the fiber bundles of raw hemp, and the fiber diameter varies between 15 and 250 μm . The bleached cellulose has a smoother, more uniform surface structure than the raw hemp fibers, which exhibit a heterogeneous and irregular fiber structure due to the presence of impurities like lignin and hemicellulose (Figure 2b). The bleached cellulose fiber diameter was observed to change between 1.6 and 15 μm .

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of hemp (a) and bleached cellulose (b)

Table 1 lists the solubility of cellulose and modified cellulose samples in different solvents and concentrations for the electrospinning process. Accordingly, cellulose was found to be insoluble in DMAc/LiCl, THF, KOH, and DMAc/LiCl/urea solvents, whereas it dissolved in LiOH and NaOH solutions. The solubility behavior may be attributed to the crystalline structure of cellulose, which is reinforced by intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonds. Dissolution becomes possible when the hydrogen bonds are weakened [6]. To enhance the solubility and alter the physicochemical properties of cellulose, we performed TEMPO modification [7]. TEMPO-modified cellulose is obtained by oxidation of hydroxyl groups on the cellulose to carboxyl groups. In this direction, TEMPO-modified cellulose was partially dissolved in DMAc/LiCl, DMAc/LiCl/urea, and [BMIM]Cl solutions, but it was not dissolved in THF.

Table 1. Solvent-dependent dissolution behavior and electrospinnability of cellulose and modified cellulose

Product name	Solvent	Concentration	Dissolution	Electrospinning
Cellulose	DMAc + LiCl (10 % wt)	3 % wt	insoluble	--
TEMPO / Cellulose	DMAc + LiCl (10 % wt)	3 % wt	soluble	low yield
TEMPO / Cellulose	DMAc + LiCl (8 % wt)	3 % wt	insoluble	--
Cellulose (in H ₂ SO ₄)	DMAc + LiCl (10 % wt)	5 % wt	soluble	fail throw
Cellulose	THF	3 % wt	insoluble	--
TEMPO / Cellulose	THF	3 % wt	insoluble	--
Cellulose	LiOH	1, 2 and 3 % wt	soluble	fail throw
Cellulose	NaOH	1, 2 and 3 % wt	soluble	fail throw
Cellulose	KOH	3 % wt	insoluble	--
Cellulose	LiCl (10 % wt) + DMAc urea (12 % wt)	3 % wt	insoluble	--
TEMPO / Cellulose	LiCl (10 % wt) + DMAc urea (12 % wt)	3 % wt	soluble	fail throw
TEMPO / Cellulose	DMAc + LiCl (10 % wt)	2 % wt	soluble	low yield
TEMPO / Cellulose	([BMIM]Cl): DMAc (1:1) + LiCl (10 % wt)	5 % wt	soluble	low yield
Cellulose Triacetate	[BMIM]Cl	8 % wt	soluble	low yield

The unstable jet formation can be attributed to solution parameters such as viscosity, concentration, electrical conductivity, and surface tension, all of which play crucial roles in electrospun fiber formation [8]. Fiber production was not achieved through electrospinning using the solutions prepared in Table 1, possibly due to the low molecular weight of the extracted cellulose.

Subsequently, efforts have been made to produce cellulose acetate fiber, considered one of the most valuable cellulose derivatives. Cellulose acetate is obtained by esterifying cellulose with acetic acid. The resulting derivatives include cellulose diacetate (CDA) and cellulose triacetate (CTA), which are partially and completely modified, respectively. By replacing the hydroxyl groups of cellulose with acetyl groups, cellulose acetate gains improved solubility and processability [9]. SEM micrographs of CDA and CTA derived from hemp are presented in Figure 3, revealing their higher porosity compared to cellulose. This increased porosity offers advantages in applications such as filtration.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of CDA (a) and CTA (b)

FTIR spectra of hemp, cellulose, and its derived are shown in Figure 4a. In the spectra of cellulose and hemp, characteristic bands appear around 3324 cm^{-1} and 2887 cm^{-1} , corresponding to hydroxyl and methyl groups, respectively. The bands observed at 1052 cm^{-1} and 894 cm^{-1} are attributed to C-O and C-C bonds within the glycosidic units of cellulose. The successful esterification of cellulose is confirmed by the complete disappearance of the -OH-band and the appearance of a carbonyl (C=O) band at approximately 1741 cm^{-1} in the cellulose acetate. Furthermore, cellulose acetates exhibit characteristic bands at 1374 cm^{-1} and 1220 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C-H and C-O vibrations of acetyl groups [10]. Notably, the intensity of the band at 894 cm^{-1} observed in cellulose increases in cellulose acetate samples.

Figure 4. FTIR (a), TGA (b), and XRD (c) graphs of hemp, cellulose, and cellulose acetate samples

Figure 4b shows the thermal stability profiles of hemp, cellulose, and cellulose acetates. Thermal decomposition of samples was performed from 30 °C to 600 °C at 10 °C/min and evaluated based on percent mass loss. According to Figure 4b, two decomposition stages were observed in the curves, corresponding to the slow and fast pyrolysis stages. The initial decomposition (between 30 °C and 100 °C) was associated with removing moisture from the samples and the evaporation of low molecular weight volatiles. The second degradation, which occurs between 200 °C and 400 °C , is the thermal degradation of the glycosidic chains of cellulose [11].

The crystal structure of hemp, cellulose, and cellulose acetates is illustrated in Figure 4c. XRD pattern of cellulose exhibits typical diffraction signals corresponding to its crystal structure at 2θ values

of 15.5°, 16.7°, and 23.0° [12]. Hemp displays a diffraction pattern similar to that of cellulose, with the highest intensity at 22.9° representing both amorphous and crystalline phases, while the lowest intensities at 16.6° and 15.2° indicate the amorphous phase [13]. Cellulose acetate samples show a prominent signal at 16.6°, characteristic of semi-crystalline acetylated cellulose derivatives. Additionally, weaker diffraction signals are observed at 14.8°, 19.0°, and 22.3° for CTA, and at 14.8°, 19.1°, and 22.4° for CDA.

Table 2. Electrospinnability of CDA and CTA using different solvents at 20 kV, 15 cm, and 1 mL/h

Electrospinning parameters	SEM micrograph	Electrospinning parameters	SEM micrograph
CDA (16 % wt) Acetone			
CDA (20 % wt) Acetone:DMAc (2:1)			
CDA (16 % wt) Acetone:DMAc (1:2) +1.8 %LiCl			
CDA (16 % wt) Acetone:Water (85%:15%)			
CTA (16 % wt) Acetone: DMAc (1:4)			
CTA (20 % wt) Acetone: DMAc (2:1)			

Nanofibers of CDA and CTA were attempted via electrospinning. Since solvent properties play a crucial role in fiber formation during this process, electrospinning solutions were prepared using various

solvents, including acetone, DMAc, DMF, and water. Table 2 presents the conditions under which these solutions were electrospun, specifically a voltage of 20 kV, a distance of 15 cm, and a flow rate of 1 mL/h. SEM micrographs indicated that neither varying the solvent type nor altering the solution concentration successfully produced distinct fiber structures for either type of acetate. However, changes in solvent type and solution concentration resulted in noticeable morphological variations. For instance, in CDA samples (16 % wt) prepared with Acetone:DMAc and Acetone:DMAc:LiCl, dimple-like beads on nanolace structures were observed. As the polymer concentration increased, the nanolace structures disappeared, replaced by larger diameter dimple-like beads or beads. Differently, spinodal structures observed in CTA sample (16 % wt) prepared with Acetone:DMAc (2:1) result from phase separation due to thermodynamic instability [14]. As the polymer concentration increases, these spinodal structures transform into dimple-like beads. The two distinct nanostructures highlighted by a red rectangle in Table 2 were compared with those of their respective bulk forms. The zeta potential and particle size of the CDA and CTA samples are listed in Table 3. After electrospinning, the observed increase in zeta potential and decrease in particle size in both acetate samples can be attributed to the alignment and stretching of polymer chains during the electrospinning. This process is thought to have increased the roughness or surface area of the materials, which contributed to more negative charge accumulation and a reduction in particle size [15].

Table 3. Comparison of zeta potential and particle size of CDA and CTA before and after electrospinning

	Zeta Potantial (mV)	Particle Size (μm)
CDA (bulk)	-28.10 ± 0.347	1.79 ± 0.18
CDA nanolace	-40.76 ± 0.650	1.05 ± 0.14
CTA (bulk)	-31.19 ± 0.443	1.74 ± 0.88
CTA beads	-39.05 ± 0.344	1.41 ± 0.92

Bulk form of CTA exhibits a higher zeta potential and smaller particle size compared to that of CDA, suggesting greater stability and sensitivity to surface interactions. These properties confer advantages for MB sorption, making CTA the preferred choice for the sorption experiments.

Another parameter affecting fiber formation is the system parameters, such as flow rate, the distance between the collector and needle, and applied voltage, which collectively influence both fiber production and the morphological appearance of the resulting fibers [16]. Table 4 presents SEM micrographs of electrospun derived CTA nanostructures obtained under varied parameters. However, the beaded structures were predominantly formed instead of well-defined fiber structures.

Table 4. SEM micrographs of CTA nanostructures formed in different electrospinning parameters

CTA (10 %wt) / DCM: DMAc (1:9)			
Electrospinning parameters	SEM micrograph	Electrospinning parameters	SEM micrograph
20 kV, 10 cm, 1 mL/h			
15 kV, 15 cm, 1 mL/h			

Figure 6 shows the sorption behavior of CTA as a function of the solution pH and contact time. The solution pH significantly influences the charge distribution on the sorbent surface, making it a critical variable in aqueous dye sorption systems [17]. As illustrated in Figure 6a, MB sorption relatively increases across a wide pH range (3-11), and the highest sorption efficiency was observed at neutral pH. In this range, MB sorption varies between 78% and 87%, highlighting its suitability for applications involving water with a neutral pH. Figure 6b presents the effect of contact time on MB sorption at different concentrations and the data applied to the pseudo-second-order kinetic model. The graphs demonstrate a rapid sorption stage within the first 60 minutes, followed by a slower sorption stage.

Figure 6. Effect of solution pH (sorbent amount: 5 mg, initial concentration: 5 mg L⁻¹, volume: 3 mL, effect time: 10 min) (a), effect time at different concentrations (sorbent amount: 10 mg, pH: 7, volume: 10 mL) (b) on MB sorption

Conclusion

This study provided preliminary insights into the challenges associated with electrospun cellulose nanofibers from hemp. The encountered challenges in obtaining cellulose nanofibers are possibly due to the low molecular weight of cellulose, limiting the ability to reach the critical concentration required for successful electrospinning. Control over solution parameters, such as conductivity, surface tension, and solvent type, remains crucial for optimizing fiber formation. Further investigations are essential to fully comprehend and address the solubility of hemp-derived cellulose and overcome the obstacles in producing electrospun fibers from cellulose solutions. Moreover, hemp-derived cellulose acetate demonstrated effective sorption capabilities for removing MB, highlighting its potential as an eco-friendly adsorbent in environmental remediation.

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